

Residue-Level Feature Extraction from Protein–Peptide Complexes for Machine Learning Applications

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Abstract

In order to apply machine learning approaches for protein–peptide interaction analysis, it requires structured and quantitative features derived from three-dimensional molecular data. However, many existing workflows either rely on external tools or lack modular, lightweight implementations suitable for rapid feature engineering. Here, in this study I present a Python-based pipeline for residue-level feature extraction from protein–peptide complexes using Protein Data Bank (PDB) structures. The pipeline parses atomic coordinates using Biopython and computes a set of geometric, physicochemical, and interface-related descriptor. This descriptor includes distance-based metrics, contact counts, residue properties and flexibility proxies. The system is designed as a modular, reproducible pipeline that produces machine learning feature tables automatically. This approach provides a foundation for downstream predictive modeling tasks such as interface classification and binding prediction.

1. Introduction

Protein–peptide interactions play a critical role in various biological processes which include signal transduction, enzyme regulation, and molecular recognition. Understanding these interactions at the residue level is important for its applications in drug discovery, protein engineering, and computational biology. With the immensely increase in application of machine learning methods in structural biology, there is a growing need for reliable and interpretable feature representations derived from molecular structures. While raw PDB files contain rich spatial information, they are not directly suitable for machine learning models. Therefore, this information needs to be transformed into structured numerical features that capture geometric relationships and physicochemical properties. Existing solutions to this problem often rely on complex modelling structure or external visualization tools, which could further limit reproducibility and scalability. Therefore, there is a need for a lightweight, Python-based approach that enables direct feature extraction from structural data in a modular and extensible manner.

2. Methods

2.1 Parsing Structural Data

The protein–peptide complex structures are obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB) [1]. The pipeline uses the Bio python PDB Parser to convert raw PDB text files into a hierarchical representation [2]. This conversion consists of models, chains, residues, and atoms. This allows sufficient repetition over structural elements and access to atomic coordinates and metadata such as B-factors. Protein and peptide chains are identified using residue count based heuristics, where shorter chains are classified as peptides and longer chains are classified as proteins.

2.2 Feature Extraction

For each residue in the protein chain, a set of features is allotted computationally using atomic coordinates and residue identity. These features are a) Geometric Features- this feature determines the minimum distance between residue atoms and peptide atoms. It also measures distance between residue centroid and peptide centre of mass. It can figure out the local density of nearby peptide atoms within a specified radius like 8 Å. b) Interface and Contact Features – this feature can interface flag based on a distance threshold such as < 5 Å. It can also contact counts representing the number of residue atoms within 4 Å and 6 Å of the peptide. c) Physicochemical features such as residue charge (-1, 0, +1), polarity and charge flags, aromaticity indicators and hydrophobicity scores based on the Kyte–Doolittle scale. And finally, d) Flexibility proxy which determines mean B-factor of atoms within each residue, representing local structural flexibility [3]. The complete pipeline is constructed in Python using standard scientific libraries which includes NumPy and Pandas for numerical operations and data handling. Structural parsing is performed using the Bio python PDB module. The pipeline is designed to operate without depending on external molecular visualization or modelling tools. This therefore, ensure portability and reproducibility of the pipeline. All computation features are well defined and can be reproduced from the same input PDB files.

3. Pipeline Design

The structure is implemented as a modular Python pipeline with clear separation for geometry module for distance and spatial calculations, physicochemical module for residue property encoding and pipeline script for synchronization and data aggregation. This pipeline design ensures a) reusability of feature functions. b) ease of extension for additional descriptors and c) consistency in feature generation. The reproducibility of the workflow is maintained through computations framework. And the validation for result output is performed using sanity checks on feature ranges and data integrity.

4. Results and Demonstration

The pipeline presented in this study was applied to a representative protein–peptide complex (PDB ID: 2EGN), which consists of a PDZ domain bound to a short peptide. After the application it successfully generated a residue-level feature table containing geometric and physicochemical descriptors for each protein residue. The pipeline was able to identify interface residues based on proximity thresholds and contact counts of the highlighted regions of interaction with the peptide. Thus, the resultant table was directly compatible with machine learning workflows and can be used for tasks such as classification or regression.

5. Discussion

The presented pipeline in this study provides a simple yet effective approach for transforming structural data into machine learning ready features. Its modular design allows researchers to adapt and extend feature definitions according to specific applications. Such as protein–peptide binding prediction, interface residue classification and feature engineering for structural machine learning models. Although being effective in its approach, this pipeline has its own limitations such as a) it does not include explicit solvent accessibility (SASA) calculations. b) does not incorporate energy-based or force-field descriptors and c) it relies on

simple heuristics for chain classification. Future study may include integration of more advanced structural descriptors and incorporation of sequence-based features.

6. Conclusion

I developed a lightweight, Python-based structure for residue-level feature extraction from protein–peptide complexes. By combining geometric, physicochemical and flexibility based descriptors, the pipeline produces framed outputs suitable for machine learning applications. This work provides a practical and extensible foundation for computational analysis of protein–peptide interactions.

7. Data and Code Availability

The source code for the feature extraction pipeline is publicly available at: <https://github.com/TaufiaHussain/cheminformatics-pdb-features>. Example input structures were obtained from the Protein Data Bank (PDB), including the protein–peptide complex with PDB ID: 2EGN. The generated feature tables and example outputs are included in the repository.

References

- 1 Berman, H. M., Westbrook, J., Feng, Z., et al. (2000). The Protein Data Bank. *Nucleic Acids Research*, 28(1), 235–242.
- 2 Cock, P. J. A., Antao, T., Chang, J. T., et al. (2009). Biopython: freely available Python tools for computational molecular biology and bioinformatics. *Bioinformatics*, 25(11), 1422–1423.
- 3 Kyte, J., & Doolittle, R. F. (1982). A simple method for displaying the hydropathic character of a protein. *Journal of Molecular Biology*, 157(1), 105–132.
- 4 Jones, S., & Thornton, J. M. (1997). Analysis of protein–protein interaction sites using surface patches. *Journal of Molecular Biology*, 272(1), 121–132.
- 5 Leach, A. R. (2001). *Molecular Modelling: Principles and Applications*. Pearson Education.